

Photonic-amplified QD@Host perovskite solar cells

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ABSTRACT

Quantum dots-in-host (QD@Host) hetero-semiconductors have a set of properties of conspicuous interest for photovoltaic (PV) applications, such as photogeneration beyond the standard semiconductor bandgap absorption limit — enabling substantially broader exploitation of the solar spectrum. Nevertheless, a key aspect has remained thus far unexploited: coupling these features with advanced light-management techniques can pronouncedly improve the overall behaviour of solar cells by boosting the QDs absorption at the desired spectral range. Hence, this work studied the achievable optical benefits of optimized QD@Host absorber materials (namely PbS@Perovskite) incorporated in solar cells, and of compounding those gains with the addition of light-trapping (LT) from photonic structures. For that, a semi-classical optical method was developed, capable of exploring the addition of quantum-enabled photo-generation from the QDs in thin perovskite-based PV cells. A smart-search design optimization was then performed for both planar and photonic-enhanced solar cells. In the latter case, the objective was to maximize resonant LT to amplify the QD-generated absorption. The optimized structures revealed significant below-bandgap absorption produced via embedded QDs, without detriments to the above-bandgap absorption mainly occurring in the host perovskite, which is shown to lead to photocurrent gains reaching 30 %. Adding the LT structures managed to further increase the absorption by ~20 % (up to 50 % total enhancement relative to the pristine cells). Remarkably, while the pristine devices photocurrent is below the standard Shockley-Queisser limit for single-bandgap cells, as expected, the LT-enhanced QD@Host solar cells managed to surpass this limit by 46 %, underlining the outstanding potential of this technology.

1. Introduction

The quantum-confinement properties of quantum dots (QDs) have led to extensive research interest, spanning many applications [1–7]. This is a direct consequence of their small size, that enables a strong electronic confinement regime [2,8] — energy levels become discrete. Moreover, these properties can be carefully tuned by changing the QD size and surrounding medium [1,9]. This capability is of notable interest for the area of solar cells, since the confined energy levels can be adjusted to customise the photo-generation profile of the absorber media and thus allow full exploitation of the solar spectrum. For instance, as explored in this work, energetically-aligned confined levels lying inside the bandgap of a host absorber allow for the extension of the intrinsic absorption properties of the material, as proposed via the intermediate band solar cell (IBSC) concept [10–15]. As such, QD@Host materials show promise at surpassing the well-known Shockley-Queisser (SQ) limit of photovoltaic (PV) technology [16–18]. Furthermore, it was

recently revealed that, despite the strong confinement provided by such nanostructures, their absorption coefficient can reach values ($\sim 10^4$ – 10^5 cm^{-1}) comparable to [19–21], or even surpassing [22], those of conventional bulk semiconductors. Notably, for the practical realization of this concept, colloidal PbS QDs@Perovskite host have shown particularly remarkable structural compatibility and resulting optoelectronic properties. [23–25], demonstrating up to 26.1 % efficiencies in perovskite solar cell (PSC) structures. Moreover, several other experimental research developments have verified key requirements for the feasibility of this technology, such as: 1) structural stability and QD and host compatibility [25]; 2) suppression of phase-transition in perovskite due to surface defects or oxidation [26]; and 3) voltage preservation, two-photon below bandgap absorption, and the occurrence of both these effects concomitantly [17]. Also, such class of nanostructured hetero-semiconductors offer the added advantage of fabrication via highly-scalable wet-coating processes, as the colloidal dots can be mixed in the perovskite in solution phase before the film crystallization [19,

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27–32].

The search for widely applicable (e.g. inexpensive, mechanically flexible) solar cells is often limited by the thickness of the semiconductor absorber. It is well-known that lower material thickness results in limited absorption, which turns out to be a severe trade-off, as the solar cell performance is directly linked with its absorption capacity. Efficient light-management techniques are thus important to expand the application range of solar cells to other areas beyond the traditional bulky and rigid PV modules [33–38]. Such photonic schemes can be realized by structuring the solar cell at wavelength-scale dimensions, namely its absorber or other adjacent layers/coatings composing the devices. The nano/micro-structuring enables broadband geometrical anti-reflection while also scattering light at closer-to-plane directions. This allows for the creation of resonant waveguided modes inside the absorber layer that can pronouncedly (by orders of magnitude) increase the solar cell absorption at the target wavelengths [39,40]. The body of literature for light-trapping (LT) structures is quite extensive, with many different and creative technologies aiming at efficient light-capture. Some notable examples applied in PSCs are random pyramids [41], nanophotonics front [42] and back electrodes [43] and microtextured multijunction PSCs, [44–46]. In this work, we make use of front photonic contact layers made of honeycomb-structured transparent conductive oxides (TCO), as they have been shown to provide notable optical absorption gains [47,48] and can be inexpensively integrated in the cells' contact via highly scalable soft-lithography methods such as colloidal lithography [35].

As such, the core objective of this work is to explore the optical benefits of QD@Host materials in solar cell absorption, and how photonics (LT) can help boost the QD absorption by creating resonance

effects at the key QD absorption peak wavelengths. For that, we performed a full structural optimization of planar and LT-enhanced solar cells aiming to achieve the best conditions to maximize photocurrent generation. Notably, the results managed to surpass the SQ limit for the bare QD@Host solar cells by up to 20 % — value that was further increased by $\sim 20\%$ by integrating the LT structures. These results underline the remarkable possibilities of this technology.

2. Methodology

This Section summarizes the semi-classical modelling method developed for the optical simulations in this work. Since the focus is on the photonic enhancements, the QD@Host properties were taken from a previous study by the authors which employed a 4-band k.p method to determine the complex refractive index spectra of PbS@Perovskite materials, as presented in Supplementary Material Section S2. Here, we highlight the choice of the MAPbBr₃ perovskite as the absorber material. Its large bandgap (~ 2.3 eV) allows a configuration close to the optimal already determined by Okada et al., [49] namely to guarantee deep and properly energetically-separated in-gap energy levels, thus enabling QD@Host behaviour matching the IBSC ideal design [20,21].

Fig. 1 depicts the main elements of this section. Firstly, Fig. 1 (c) and (d) show the schematics of the studied solar cells. Both schematics are centred around the core PSC device configuration, namely: back contact, hole transport layer (HTL), perovskite absorber, electron transport layer (ETL) and top TCO contact. This configuration is quite standard and has been extensively employed in the literature [4,33,47,50]. The materials used for each layer are summarized in Table 1 together with the references for the corresponding optical properties. This data is available in a

Fig. 1. (a) Schematic representation of the optical analysis performed in this work. The first step is the calculation of the QD@Host optical properties, (complex refractive index) followed by the result's validation. The simulations are then performed both for: (c) planar structures (see list of layers' materials in Table 1), where the core variables are the TCO and HTL thicknesses indicated by the arrows in the schematic; and (d) for a LT structure composed of an hexagonal array (honeycomb) of vertically aligned semi-spheroidal voids, with in-plane radius (R) and height (R_z). The variable quantities, namely TCO and HTL thicknesses, R , R_z and array pitch, are indicated by the arrows in the schematic. The last step is a particle-swarm optimization (PSO) to determine the ideal parameters for each structure. (b) Schematic band diagram of an intermediate band solar cell (IBSC), representing the 3 main photon transitions: (1) valence band (VB) to intermediate band (IB), (2) IB to conduction band (CB), and (3) standard VB to CB transition in host material.

Table 1

Summary of materials and thicknesses used for the studied solar cells, shown in Fig. 1. The refractive index spectra for these materials (referenced in the second line of the table) are shown in Supplementary Material Section S1. In the thickness line, the “(var)” entries indicate that the parameter is a variable for optimization. The “Top Contact” thickness is a variable in both LT and planar architectures.

	Back Contact	HTL	Perovskite	ETL	Top Contact	LT Structures
Materials	Ag [53]	Spiro-OMeTAD [54]	MAPbBr ₃ [55]	TiO ₂ [56]	ITO [57]	ITO [57]
Thickness (nm)	120	(var)	500	10	(var)	(var)

web database (reference [51]) and is also plotted in Supplementary Material Section S1.

Fig. 1 (b) shows a schematic band diagram for an intermediate band solar cell (IBSC), highlighting the intermediate mini-band (IB) created by the energetically-aligned ground-states of the QDs embedded in the host semiconductor. Notably, this IB enables two-photon electronic transitions (labelled 1 and 2), beyond the traditional valence-conduction band transition (labelled 3), that expand the wavelength range of the solar spectrum available for photocurrent generation [17,28,31]. This is the key concept of the PV technology in study in this work.

For the planar solar cell (Fig. 1 (c)) the variables of interest are simply the layers' thicknesses. Here only the thickness of the HTL (Spiro-OMeTAD, henceforth Spiro) and TCO (ITO) layers was chosen to be optimized, as indicated by the arrows in Fig. 1 (c). The perovskite, back contact and the ETL layer's thickness was fixed at 500, 120 and 10 nm, respectively, in accordance with state-of-art configurations commonly found in the literature [50]. The LT-enhanced solar cells — shown in Fig. 1 (d) — have further optimization variables besides the standard layer thicknesses. Namely, the radius (R), height (Rz) and distance of the voids composing the honeycomb structure (indicated by the arrows in Fig. 1 (d)). All these parameters were optimization variables, as they are the main design elements to maximize the quantum-generated absorption from the QD@Host materials.

The first steps in the optical modelling (red box in Fig. 1 (a)) consist in the validation of the simulations' configuration, and the fitting of the optical properties of the materials. In the first case, an overall mesh for the simulation is defined ensuring proper accuracy and precision for the results in the entire search domain. This is particularly important when changing the structural properties of the device — as is the case under iterative multi-variable smart-search optimizations. This analysis is shown in Supplementary Material Section S3. The fitting of the optical properties of the materials is a particularity of time-dependent numeric simulations, and a fundamental step to guarantee their proper convergence. Essentially, both real and imaginary part of the refractive index must obey the Kramers-Kronig relations [52]. Here, the mixed quantum-classical nature of the refractive indices used required the splitting of each simulation in two different steps for photon energies above and below the host bandgap, as further explained in Section 3.1, namely one ranging from wavelengths between 400 and 550 nm and the other from 550 nm to 1100 nm.

For the full device modelling, the finite-difference time domain (FDTD) method can calculate forthwith the absorbed power density (P_{Abs}) (Equation (1)) for each material in the solar cell, calculated from the electric field \mathbf{E} distribution, the imaginary part of the dielectric permittivity ($\text{Im}\{\epsilon(\mathbf{r},\omega)\}$) and the angular frequency ω [58]. It is important to note that, due to the nature of the FDTD simulations, this value often comes normalized by the incident source power, such that the units become m^{-3} rather than Wm^{-3} .

$$P_{\text{Abs}}(\mathbf{r}, \omega) = -\frac{1}{2} \omega |\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{r}, \omega)|^2 \text{Im}\{\epsilon(\mathbf{r}, \omega)\} \quad (1)$$

The two other main quantities analysed are: (1) the photogeneration rate (G), that indicates the number of photons absorbed per unit volume, and (2) the optical current density (J_{ph}), that represents the photogeneration rate within the cell absorber layer integrated in volume and in wavelength. This is then the main figure-of-merit (FoM) to rate the optical performance of the solar cells. The first quantity is determined by

integrating the ratio between the absorbed power density and the photon energy ($E_{\text{ph}} = \hbar\omega$) as described in Equation (2). The optical photocurrent is determined from the total absorption ($\text{Abs} = \int_V P_{\text{Abs}} dV$) solely in the absorber layer convoluted with the solar spectrum ($I_{\text{AM1.5G}}$) as described in Equation (3).

$$G = \int \frac{P_{\text{Abs}}}{\hbar\omega} d\omega \quad (2)$$

$$J_{\text{ph}} = e \int \frac{\lambda}{hc} \text{Abs}(\lambda) I_{\text{AM1.5G}}(\lambda) d\lambda \quad (3)$$

For a QD@Host system the “Abs” spectrum results from two main components associated with the QDs and host materials. To account for the dots-mediated photocurrent generation, the absorption pertaining to the VB-IB transition was the main transition process considered in this work. Here, it could be argued the need for an internal quantum efficiency (IQE) variable that represents the internal conversion efficiency of the QDs, but the calculated transition rate already takes such effect into account. Besides, owing to the focus of this work on the achievable optical performance of this class of photonic-enhanced IBSC devices, it was considered that the IB-CB transition always takes place (i.e. has relatively high transition rate). As such, such transition was disregarded in the present study for sake of simplicity of the optical analysis. Nevertheless, this is a current limitation of the present model that should be addressed for the full accounting of the generated charge carriers, particularly when considering further electrical simulations.

3. Results

This Section outlines the core results of this work. Initially, it focuses on the fitting of the QD@Host properties. This is particularly important, as the quantum nature of the k.p-computed refractive index spectra interferes with the FDTD requirement that the optical properties satisfy the Kramers-Kronig relations. Subsequently, the focus shifts to the structural optimization of the planar and LT-enhanced solar cells architecture. Lastly, an overview is provided on the optimized results, comparing between pristine and QD@Host absorber materials, as well as with integration of the LT structures in the devices.

3.1. Fitting of QD@Host optical properties

In the FDTD method, the fitting of the solar cell materials' optical properties is an often overlooked, but important, aspect of the simulation procedure. The time-dependent nature of the FDTD method makes it particularly dependent on the “classical behaviour” of the optical dispersion properties of the solar cell materials — essentially, they must satisfy the Kramers-Kronig relations — to guarantee the computation stability/convergence [52,59]. On that note, the here-used *Ansys Lumerical* software package has a database where the complex refractive index spectra can be imported and, before each simulation, both the real and imaginary parts are fitted for the subsequent simulation via a multi-coefficient approach which guarantees that the Kramers-Kronig relations are met [60]. This is mostly governed by two main factors. First, the number of coefficients used in the polynomial fitting procedure: the more coefficients used the more accurate the fitting, but also the more time demanding. Secondly, the fitting tolerance: lower tolerances require more iterations, which increase the fitting accuracy, also at the

expense of computational time [60].

For the case of QD@Host materials, the non-classical nature of the k . p method used to determine the refractive index leads to several problems during the fitting procedure, mainly because of the spectrally sharp absorption peaks arising from the discrete quantum-confined energy levels. Supplementary Information Fig. S2 makes it evident that, for the standard behaviour of the FDTD method, it is unrealistic to accurately fit such QD@Host response, as even the higher quality fitting settings (Supplementary Information Figure S2 (c)) can miss several of the sub-bandgap absorption peaks. The essential reason for such disproportionate fittings lies in the fact that the Kramers-Kronig relations require both real and imaginary components of the refractive index to be connected. Thus, when the QD-only optical properties are built from the bulk-QD real refractive index and k . p -computed imaginary refractive index [21], the interactions of both components generally do not satisfy the Kramers-Kronig relations. Thence, when combined with the perovskite material during the fitting procedure, the algorithm tries to compensate the added quantum features by changing the real part of the refractive index of the material. This effect is well seen in Supplementary Information Fig. S3.

To circumvent this issue, a different methodology was devised which can find application in other semi-classical approaches. The way found, without adding complexity to the quantum-part of the calculations, was to spectrally split the simulation into two segments (separated by the bandgap of the perovskite host material, ~ 550 nm), given that the QD properties mostly influence the refractive index for sub-bandgap energies, while the above-bandgap range is chiefly determined by the host

medium. Fig. 2 shows an extensive comparison between the fittings in both methods. This comparison was performed for different fitting tolerances and number of coefficients, aiming at determining which method converges faster and provides more accurate results.

Fig. 2 (a) shows an example kernel density profile for a particular tolerance and number of coefficients, to clarify the analysis of the results in Fig. 2 (c) and (d). This profile indicates the frequency of simulations that fall into a specific root-mean squared (RMS) value calculated from the FDTD fitting to the imported data. Moreover, for each tolerance and number of coefficients, 500 random QD@Host properties were calculated, fitted and summarized into kernel density profiles. The resulting fittings for the different tolerances and number of coefficients are shown in Fig. 2(c) and (d) for the single-run method (default FDTD method across the full spectrum) and double-run method (performing two distinct fittings in two spectral regions below and above the host bandgap), respectively. Here, the colour of each profile is a direct reference to the mean value of the RMS, to facilitate comparison between both results.

It is evident that the double-run method provides much better fitting, as it not only reaches lower average RMS values, but also provides smaller variations in the RMS fittings for different QD@Host materials, particularly for lower tolerances and higher fitting coefficients. For the following studies, we chose a value of 0.01 for the fitting tolerance and 17 for the number of coefficients, as it is often preferred to have lower tolerance and lower number of coefficients. Figs. S3 and S4 in Supplementary Information show the comparison between the final results.

Fig. 2. (a) Kernel density profile of the RMS fitting of 500 random QD@Host materials. This profile is shown as an example for each of the profiles in (c) and (d). (b) Illustrative PbS@Perovskite refractive index spectrum, indicating the wavelength ranges used for the single-run and double-run fitting procedures and the respective fit for the refractive index spectrum using the double-run method. (c) Root mean square fitting dependence on the tolerance and fitting coefficients from the FDTD software for the single-run method. The colour of each plot indicates the mean value of the RMS, as described in plot (a); (d) Root mean square fitting dependence on the tolerance and fitting coefficients for the double-run method.

3.2. Planar optimization

This section focuses on the optical optimization of the planar (without LT) solar cells. The optimization variables and the materials used are defined in the Methodology (Section 2), while the cell configuration schematic is shown in Fig. 1. Namely, the device layers are: Ag (120 nm)/Spiro (t_{HTL})/Perovskite (500 nm)/TiO₂ (10 nm)/ITO (t_{TCO}), where the thicknesses (t) of the HTL and TCO layers are optimization variables. As for the QDs, two sets of PbS dots optimized in a previous work by the authors were selected [21], namely with 0.08 m_0 and 0.15 m_0 effective mass with radius of 2.87 nm and 2.44 nm, respectively. A Bruggeman volumetric density factor of 0.4 is considered for the QDs concentration within the host material to determine the combined PbS@Perovskite refractive index spectra.

Unlike in the following section, in the present case of a two-variable optimization the entire search domain is scanned with a two-parameter sweep, allowing direct visualization of the full assessed domain. Fig. 3 shows these results for the pristine perovskite (left profile), the 2.44 nm (middle profile) and 2.87 nm (right profile) radius QD@Host materials, while Table 2 shows the optimized properties that yield highest photocurrent density (FoM, resulting from integrated absorption — see Equation (3)). The current density values are relatively low, specially with the pristine absorber without QDs, as would be expected from such a high bandgap (2.3 eV) perovskite material. Nevertheless, these results show a clear increase in the overall optical absorption due to the QDs inclusion when compared to the perovskite-only absorption (two last columns in Table 2).

Further results are also provided in Section 3.4, where the outcomes with both LT and planar cell architectures are directly contrasted, and the highest attained photocurrent values are compared with the theoretical ones from the Shockley-Queisser single-junction limit for such wide-bandgap PSCs.

The optimization results indicate a general preference for lower Spiro and ITO thicknesses. More specifically, for the smaller QDs the optimal thicknesses were 100 nm for ITO and 210 nm for Spiro, while for the larger QD the thicknesses were 100 nm ITO and 186 nm Spiro (Table 2). This can be explained by two main competing effects. Firstly, there is the unwanted parasitic absorption from both layers that, from an optical point of view, leads to directly minimize the thickness of these layers. Interestingly, if the minimum thickness values for both materials

Table 2

Summary of the optimized planar solar cell structures (without LT) for the host-only (reference) and QD@Host absorbers. Here, t_{HTL} and t_{TCO} are the thicknesses of the Spiro and ITO layers, respectively, and Optimized J_{ph} is the maximum photocurrent density attained in each case.

QD Radius (nm)	Effective Mass (m_0)	t_{HTL} (nm)	t_{TCO} (nm)	Optimized J_{ph} (mA/cm ²)
-	-	131	173	7.5
2.44	0.15 m_0	210	100	10.0
2.87	0.08 m_0	186	100	9.5

were to be lower, it is highly likely that the best pair of parameters would converge even for smaller values of thickness. Nevertheless, thicknesses below the simulated values are unreasonable from a fabrication and electrical point of view, thence the choice to set a lower limit of these values to 100 nm in order to ensure their selective contact role in the devices. Secondly, there is the anti-reflection effect in the ITO layer also related with constructive and destructive interference of the incident light. Such effect is particularly noticeable in the wave-like pattern of both profiles in Fig. 3, a direct characteristic of interference. This has the tendency to shift the optimized values from the minimum defined for the optimization, since the most beneficial interference effects occur with higher thicknesses. Interestingly, the pristine planar cell does not follow this same trend.

3.3. Light-trapping optimization

The use of photonic wavelength-scale structuring integrated in the cells front contact provides additional degrees of freedom to those of the planar devices shown above, with strong potential to amplify the absorption properties of the combined QD@Host media. A schematic of these structures is shown in Fig. 1 (d), while the respective materials/layers/thicknesses and optimization variables are summarized in Table 1. Namely, the base device layers are similar to the planar case, over which an additional void-like honeycomb-structured layer made of ITO is placed. The optimization variables are the HTL (Spiro) and TCO (ITO) thicknesses, as previously, but now together with the radius (R), height (R_z) and center-to-center distance (pitch) of the semi-prolate voids.

While the above planar structures could be forthwith optimized via a

Fig. 3. Heatmap profiles of the optical photocurrent density (J_{ph}) for planar solar cell structures shown in Fig. 1 (c), as a function of the two optimization parameters: TCO and HTL thickness. (a) Reference profile for pristine (without QDs) perovskite absorber; (b) QD@Host absorber with 2.44 nm radius QDs having effective mass of 0.08 m_0 ; (c) 2.87 nm radius QDs with effective mass of 0.15 m_0 . In both (b) and (c) we considered a Bruggeman volumetric density factor of 0.4 for the QDs concentration in the host, following the results of a previous study [21].

two-variable sweep, this is not the case for the multi-variable LT-enhanced solar cells. For that, it was necessary to use a stochastic optimization algorithm allowing smart multi-parameter search. The chosen algorithm was the particle swarm optimization (PSO), as it has been widely used in previous works for similar types of optimizations [40]. The resulting properties found for the best-performing cases are summarized in Table 3. The table also shows the limiting values of the ranges set for each variable in the optimizations. Notably, the upper bounds for the Spiro and ITO layer thicknesses are smaller (respectively 200 and 250 nm) than that employed for the planar optimization (400 nm, as seen in Fig. 3). This was chosen due to the stronger preference for lower values for the present LT cases. Furthermore, due to much increased simulation complexity of these structured solar cells, the lower set of thickness also helps to decrease the simulation time and facilitates the search for the optimal value. As a last consideration, above 200 nm thicknesses for Spiro are rarely used experimentally, while for ITO the LT-structures will assist in the conductivity of the front contact and thereby allow reduced thickness in the flat TCO underneath. This latter effect has already been shown by Sanchez-Sobrado et al. [61].

Similarly to the planar case, the thicknesses of Spiro and ITO seem to be preferably lower, with the values decreasing from the previous optimized planar ones. This reinforces the above-mentioned simplification of reducing the optimization search space. It should be noted that the flat ITO layer is below 100 nm, while in the planar case it was limited to 100 nm. Here, the lower limit of such ITO layer underneath the LT structures was reduced to 50 nm, owing to the fact that the front structures are also ITO-based and thus the combined minima of both ITO layer and void height (Rz) define the new lower acceptable ITO limit of 100 nm, as also demonstrated in the work of Sanchez-Sobrado et al. [61]. In terms of the photonic structures geometry, there seems to be a general trend for bigger features with both radius and height (R and Rz , respectively) above 300 nm, and the pitch close to $3R$, with the exception of the pristine solar cell. Interestingly, the photocurrent values seem to be similar between QD sizes, even though the QD absorption peaks are quite different (Fig. 5(a) and (b)). Moreover, these optimized designs do indicate an effort to increase absorption for higher wavelengths, which is something expected as the focus is to increase the below-bandgap QD-generated absorption.

The absolute photocurrent values are around 2 mA/cm^2 higher than the optimized planar results, and 3 mA/cm^2 above the pristine optimized LT solar cell. As such, the inclusion of effective LT, compounded with the previously analysed benefits from the QD@Host material, does show a significant improvement when compared with the pristine perovskite solar cells. The following section evaluates the full absorption profiles and provides a clear comparison between all the final results. Nevertheless, firstly it is relevant to analyse the internal light absorption distribution across the devices, to better understand how and where the LT effects take place. For that, Fig. 4 shows three different sets of profiles for the different studied cases. To avoid redundancy, the results are only shown for the 2.44 nm QD case considering 4 different device

configurations, namely for planar and LT-structured solar cells, as well as for perovskite absorbers with (QD@Host) and without (pristine) the embedded QDs.

The first plotted quantity is the photogeneration profile (G — described in the Methodology) that indicates the generated electron density in the device's volume, considering all absorbed photons from the full incident solar spectrum. Here, this quantity was only determined for below-bandgap wavelengths to better assess the QD-induced effects in the QD@Host absorber. The other quantity is the absorbed power density per wavelength (P_{ABS} - described in Methodology), that indicates for a specific wavelength (marked by the vertical grey line in Fig. 5) the main regions of absorption. This quantity is shown for 750 nm wavelength (second row in Fig. 4), as it corresponds to one of the main below-bandgap QD-generated absorption peaks (based on the results from Fig. 5). Similarly, the profile is also shown for 450 nm wavelength (third row in Fig. 4) to represent the above-bandgap absorption in the device, mainly caused by the perovskite host.

There are two main aspects to note from Fig. 4. First, there is the general QD@Host increased absorption relative to the pristine perovskite absorber. From the photogeneration and the absorbed power at 750 nm wavelength (first two rows in Fig. 4) it is clear that, while the parasitic absorption remains quite similar (i.e. absorption in the ITO, Spiro, TiO_2 and Ag layers), the perovskite absorption increases due to the added QD effects (Fig. 4 (a2), (b2), (c2), (d2)). Interestingly, while in the pristine cells the absorption occurring in the perovskite remains inferior to the absorption of the remaining layers (Fig. 4 (a1), (b1)) — a direct consequence of the direct and high bandgap of the material — the QDs embedment raises the perovskite absorption to values close to or higher than such parasitic absorption. Particularly for the 750 nm wavelength (second row in Fig. 4), there is a notable increase in the absorbed power of around 1–2 orders of magnitude. This is precisely the wanted result from the added QDs. The right-side profiles in Fig. 4 (a-f2) show the results with the LT structures, where the “hot-spots” of the resonance patterns resulting from light scattering and interference effects can be observed, being more noticeable at the main QD@Host absorption peaks.

The last row in Fig. 4 shows the absorbed power density profiles for 450 nm wavelength. As this is a spectral region where most light is absorbed in the host material and does not significantly interact with the QDs, the profiles are mostly similar for both pristine and QD@Host devices, with the notable exception of the Spiro/Ag back contact. Interestingly, the Spiro absorption seems to increase significantly in the QD@Host devices (Fig. 4 (e2), (f2)), while the other layers either remain mostly similar or only show a small absorption improvement — ITO and perovskite, respectively in Fig. 4 (e1), (e2), (f1), (f2). This appears to be caused by the slightly lower effective refractive index of the QD@Host material (from the used Bruggeman effective-index method) that increases the penetration of light towards the rear cell side.

3.4. Results summary

This section combines the above-optimized results for the planar and LT-enhanced solar cells, as well as for the original (pristine) perovskite absorber — without the added QDs — and for the quantum-enhanced absorber. Fig. 5 summarizes these results for both previously optimized QD sizes, showing the optimized absorption profiles (Fig. 5(a–d)) and the corresponding photocurrents (Fig. 5 (e)) for the distinct cases analysed in Sections 3.2 and 3.3. Fig. 5 (e) also indicates the photocurrent produced for photon energies above (filled bars height) and below (hashed bars height) the host perovskite bandgap, being the latter given by the added QDs as evidenced by the sub-bandgap absorption peaks in Fig. 5(a–d) at wavelengths above 550 nm. The most notable aspect is the significant rise in the overall device absorption with the addition of QDs, surpassing 30 % gain with only planar cells and even increasing to 50 % between LT pristine and LT with QD@Host absorber. Here, it is notable that most of the gains indeed come from the below

Table 3

Summary of the optimized J_{ph} for the LT-enhanced QD@Host structures, for the two different types of PbS QDs studied, and for the pristine perovskite absorber (without QDs, in 1st line). The geometrical parameters are defined in Fig. 1. The dimensional variables also show the respective domain of optimization [lower and upper bounds] below the variable.

QD radius (nm)	R (nm)	Rz (nm)	Pitch (xR)	t_{HTL} (nm)	t_{TCO} (nm)	Optimized J_{ph} (mA/cm ²)
-	[50, 500]	[50, 500]	[2,3]	[100, 200]	[50, 250]	8.2
2.44 nm	354	500	2	100	50	11.4
2.87 nm	341	427	2.7	136	50	12.0
2.87 nm	282	318	2.8	107	72	12.0

Fig. 4. Full-spectrum photogeneration profiles (G , first row), and absorbed power density (P_{ABS}) at 750 nm (second row) and 450 nm (third row) wavelengths, for the optimized planar and LT-structured solar cells (schematics in Fig. 1), for the 2.44 nm QDs. Namely, the results are shown for the optimized QD@Host planar solar cells ((a2), (c2), (e2)) and the equivalently sized pristine perovskite (without QDs in (a1), (c1), (e1)); as well as for the optimized QD@Host LT-enhanced solar cells ((b2), (d2), (f2)) and the equivalently sized pristine perovskite ((b1), (d1), (f1)).

bandgap absorption, as the differences between no-QD and QD photocurrent are similar to those between the sub-bandgap photocurrent.

A different aspect is also the small below-bandgap absorption observed for the pristine solar cells. Although this absorption should be mostly parasitic from an electrical point of view, it is still present when considering purely optical computations, due to the non-zero imaginary component of the perovskite refractive index even for the larger wavelengths. Still, from the hashed bars in Fig. 5 (e), these values are a marginal fraction of the entire absorption.

Considering the above-bandgap absorption it is notable that, for the

most part, it remains at around 7 mA/cm^2 . Beyond that, the photogeneration profiles in Fig. 4(a–d) also show a similar absorption behaviour throughout the cell volume. This is particularly relevant since, as described earlier, the Bruggeman method used to determine the QD@Host refractive index does lead to a decrease in the overall absorption occurring within the host perovskite material with the inclusion of the QDs. While in the planar results this is not directly seen in the absorption profiles, as the peaks tend to shift due to the interference patterns, the LT results between the pristine and the QD@Host absorber for the 2.8 nm radius QD do show a small decrease in above-bandgap

Fig. 5. Summary profiles for the optimized solar cell structures with the parameters in Table 3 (a), (b) Absorption profiles for the optimized planar structures, using QDs with size 2.4 nm and 2.8 nm, respectively. (c) (d) Absorption profiles for the LT-enhanced devices, for the same QD sizes. Each profile shows the absorption for two different LT and planar setups: the absorption with the optimized QD@Host absorber (full lines) and with the optimized pristine — without QDs — perovskite (dashed lines). (e) Bar chart summarizing the photocurrent density values attained for all the different studied cases: LT cells in red and planar in blue. The bottom hashed regions indicate the below-bandgap photocurrent. The percentage values indicate the relative photocurrent gains. The horizontal dotted lines indicate the short-circuit current density J_{SC} attained with the SQ limit determined for a 2.3 eV bandgap absorber and considering a maximum fill factor of 0.9 [63].

absorption (blue full and dashed lines in Fig. 5(c and d)). Nevertheless, such decrease is minimal and is compensated by the significant below-bandgap absorption. Furthermore, the absorption profiles also indicate that the LT structures optimization focused more on increasing the QD-created peaks, via scattering and establishment of guided modes inside the cell material, leaving only the bare anti-reflection effects to mitigate the optical losses in the host above the bandgap. This is evident by the increase in peak intensity shown in the absorption profiles due to the resonant LT effects.

Lastly, it was also determined the Shockley-Queisser (SQ) single-bandgap short-circuit current (J_{SC}) limit, to compare with the results

obtained for the QD@Host absorbers with a multi-bandgap electronic configuration. For a semiconductor with bandgap of 2.3 eV the efficiency limit is 15 %, while the maximum open-circuit voltage (V_{oc}) for such bandgap is around 2 V [62]. Hence, considering a theoretical maximum value for the fill factor of 0.9 [63], the obtained J_{SC} limit for the single wide-bandgap material is around 8.3 mA/cm² [62]. This value is marked by the horizontal dotted lines in Fig. 5 (e). Remarkably, such SQ limit sits precisely between the pristine and the QD-enhanced results, even considering that the pristine results show some minor below-bandgap absorption as previously noted. This is a clear indication that QD@Host materials can surpass the classical SQ limit. Notably, the

QD@Host planar solar cells show currents 20 % above this limit for the 2.4 nm QDs and 14 % for the 2.8 nm QDs. These relative gains are further improved to values of 46 % and 35 %, respectively, by the addition of the LT structures.

4. Conclusion

A semi-classical model was explored to reveal outstanding potentialities from the intriguing optical behaviour of solar cells using quantum-structured absorber materials, as well as considering photonic front structures for light-trapping. Two optimized QD@Host materials, made of PbS@Perovskite, are used to simulate planar and photonic-enhanced solar cell architectures. These were then structurally optimized to determine the best solar cell setup to enhance the added QD absorption. It was determined that the LT structures can indeed pronouncedly boost the below-bandgap absorption peaks from the QDs by creating resonant waveguided modes that act directly on the QD-generated energy transitions. The determined photocurrent gains from the photonic structuring plus addition of the QD@Host absorbers reached values of 50 % relative to pristine planar cells.

The classical Shockley-Queisser limit for single-junction, single-bandgap solar cells establishes a maximum short-circuit current density of ~ 8.3 mA/cm² with a pristine semiconductor having the same wide-bandgap of 2.3 eV. Remarkably, it was determined that the photocurrents generated by the QD@Host absorbers managed to overcome this limit by 20 % and 14 %, for the 2.44 nm and 2.87 nm QDs respectively, increasing by an additional gain of 21 % and 18 %, respectively, with the addition of the LT structures.

This is a clear indication of ground-breaking possibilities for PV technology, namely it is shown that optimized multi-band QD@Host materials can pronouncedly surpass the classical SQ limit, and that such enhancements can be strongly amplified via light-trapping effects from properly designed photonic structures. The unprecedented findings of this work are expected to foster further theoretical research, e.g. to extend the present optical analysis into the electrical domain, as well as further nano-fabrication and experimental advances aimed at experimentally verifying the envisaged potentialities.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Miguel Alexandre: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Software, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Elvira Fortunato:** Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition. **Rodrigo Martins:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition. **Manuel J. Mendes:** Writing – original draft, Supervision, Resources, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mtphys.2025.101910>.

Data availability

All the relevant code used to generate the results is available in <https://github.com/perspe/qd-host>

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